

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF IMPROVING THE SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SCHOOLS (BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF 10TH-11TH GRADES)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14251109>

Abstract. *This scientific article examines the issue of improving the socio-pedagogical system in the process of teaching foreign languages in schools. It analyzes the importance of using modern pedagogical methods and technologies to enhance the motivation, develop social skills, and improve cultural interactions of 10th-11th grade students in learning foreign languages. The main elements of the socio-pedagogical system, including the integrated approach, collaborative teaching, task-based learning, and the “flipped classroom” method, are highlighted. The necessity of professional development for teachers, the application of new technologies, and an approach tailored to the individual needs of students are emphasized. This article may serve as a practical guide for foreign language teachers and contribute to the further improvement of the socio-pedagogical system in the education sector.*

Keywords: *foreign language teaching, socio-pedagogical system, 10th-11th grades, student development, pedagogical methods, integrated approach, task-based learning, flipped classroom, collaborative teaching, educational technologies, professional development, individual approach.*

Introduction. In the era of globalization and technology, knowledge of foreign languages has become an integral part of modern society. A foreign language is not just a means of communication but also plays a crucial role in personal social and cultural development, as well as in achieving educational and professional success. The large-scale reforms in the education sector in Uzbekistan, particularly the improvement of the foreign language teaching system, are aimed at preparing personnel that meet international standards. This article explores the theoretical foundations for enhancing the socio-pedagogical system of foreign language teaching and provides practical recommendations based on the example of 10th-11th grades.

Teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan's education policy, especially in the upper grades of schools, plays a vital role in preparing students for the global world. At the same time, developing teaching methodologies and improving the socio-pedagogical system remain pressing issues. This article analyzes the necessity and methods of improving the socio-pedagogical system in foreign language teaching for 10th-11th grade students.

Key Theoretical Foundations of the Socio-Pedagogical System. The socio-pedagogical system focuses on adapting students to the social environment and fostering their interpersonal relationships during the teaching process. Improving this system in foreign language education enables students to adopt a more effective approach to learning languages. According to L.S. Vygotsky, language learning is based on social interaction, highlighting the role of social influence in the learning process. Implementing this approach in school foreign language education helps students successfully apply language in real-life situations.

The socio-pedagogical system should include the following essential elements:

1. Development of social interactions among students: Foreign language teaching should not only address linguistic goals but also include communication in social environment, understanding other cultures, and showing respect for them.

2. Role of the teacher: The teacher should contribute to the intellectual, emotional, and social development of students. Teachers play a crucial role in motivating students, building trustful communication, and applying the necessary pedagogical approaches during foreign language teaching.

3. Application of technology in the educational process: Modern technologies, including multimedia tools, online courses, and interactive platforms, enhance the effectiveness and engagement of foreign language learning.

Methods for Enhancing the Socio-Pedagogical System in Teaching Foreign Languages in 10th-11th Grades

1. Integrated approach:

Foreign language learning should not be limited to memorizing grammar and expanding vocabulary. Through an integrated approach, language learning can be connected with various subjects, cultures, and social topics. For instance, 10th-11th grade students can explore global issues, historical events, and contemporary social matters using foreign languages, boosting their motivation for language learning.

2. Project work:

Organizing campaigns and project work can effectively engage students in learning foreign languages. These activities expose students to real-life situations, enabling them to develop practical skills along with theoretical knowledge. For instance, organizing international conferences, meetings with guests from other countries, or cultural events for 10th-11th grade students can be beneficial.

3. Differentiated approach:

Every student learns individually; therefore, teaching methods should vary accordingly. Students in 10th-11th grades may have different levels of language proficiency, requiring teachers to tailor their approaches to meet the needs of each student.

4. Group work and fostering communication:

Learning a foreign language requires not only individual work but also collaboration in groups. Providing opportunities for students to work in teams, express their opinions freely, and communicate with others enhances mutual support and shared learning experiences.

Socio-Psychological Aspects of Foreign Language Teaching. Social and psychological factors play a significant role in foreign language teaching. Teachers' approaches are crucial in helping students develop self-awareness, confidence, teamwork skills, and communication abilities. Teachers should encourage students to learn from their mistakes, value their efforts, and view failures as lessons.

Interactive methods and group work can motivate students to use the foreign language in daily life, beyond academic settings. For instance, communicative games, role-playing, and video conferencing via modern technologies can teach students to apply language in practice.

Expanded Pedagogical Methods. The following advanced pedagogical methods can increase the efficiency of foreign language teaching:

1. Task-Based Learning (TBL): This method involves presenting students with tasks that require the use of foreign language to achieve specific goals. Students learn the language by completing these tasks, enhancing practical application skills.

2. Flipped Classroom Method: In this approach, students learn new topics independently (e.g., through video lessons or reading materials), and classroom time is devoted to applying the learned material in practice.

3. Collaborative Teaching: Encouraging group work, collaborative teaching enables students to learn from each other while developing social skills.

Application of new pedagogical technologies. Modern technologies can be an effective tool in foreign language teaching. For example, through online resources, mobile applications, educational programs and platforms, an opportunity to provide individual education to students is created. Grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation and writing skills can be strengthened with the help of interactive applications specially created for students of 10-11 grades. Such platforms increase students' interest in the lesson and make the teacher's work more effective.

Creating online forums and chat rooms allows foreign language students to communicate with other students or foreign teachers. This will help students develop their language skills in real life.

Training and professional development of teachers. Educators should be in constant professional development to adapt to new methods and technologies in teaching a foreign language. Making them aware of modern educational trends, developing new educational materials and teaching them to use innovative technologies increases the effectiveness of teaching. Teachers can be trained through refresher courses, seminars, sharing experiences and collaboration in social networks.

Practical recommendations. The following practical recommendations for improving the socio-pedagogical system in teaching foreign languages at school will help to teach foreign languages effectively:

1. Personalization of the educational process. The needs, abilities and interests of each student should be taken into account. Personalized learning approaches include:

Diagnostics: conducting tests and questionnaires at the beginning of the school year to determine the language readiness of students.

Individual Learning Plans: Create an individual plan for students and monitor achievement of agreed goals.

Differentiated approach: Engaging all students by using different levels of tasks in lessons. For example, giving more complex tasks for strong students, and simpler tasks for the rest.

2. Interdisciplinary integration. Linking language teaching with other subjects increases students' interest and places knowledge in a real-life context.

Combining subjects: For example, in geography lessons, students can learn about countries and climates in English.

Interdisciplinary Projects: Combining history and foreign language studies to analyze historical events in English. It helps to develop students' language skills.

STEAM approach: creating interesting projects by connecting science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics with a foreign language.

3. Improvement of the assessment system. In addition to traditional assessment methods, the following innovative assessment methods can be used:

Portfolio System: Assessing students' progress using a portfolio of their work and projects.

Formative assessment: Introduce short prompts or feedback during the lesson to motivate students and improve the process.

Performance-based assessment: Assessing students by speaking in a foreign language, defending a project, or performing real-life tasks.

4. Increase motivation. In order to increase students' interest in learning foreign languages, it is recommended to use the following strategies:

Gamification: Enriching lessons with interactive games, quizzes and contests. For example, increasing vocabulary through games or ensuring the reinforcement of rules.

Incentive system: Reward successful students with small gifts, certificates or extra points.

Taking students' personal goals into account: Determining the meaning of language learning for each student. For example, explaining how the language will be useful for future work or study.

5. Wider introduction of modern technologies. The use of technologies in the educational process increases students' interest and participation in language learning.

Mobile Apps: Apps like Duolingo, Memrise, or Quizlet help students practice vocabulary and grammar on their own.

Virtual platforms: organization of interactive lessons that allow group language learning through Google Classroom, Zoom or Microsoft Teams.

Online resources: Enrich lessons by using resources such as BBC Learning English or TedEd.

6. Development of intercultural communication. Students need to accept foreign languages not only as a language, but also as a means of learning about other cultures.

International projects: Creating opportunities for students to communicate with foreign peers. For example, interschool correspondence or online conferences.

Cultural events: organizing exhibitions on English language week, foreign culture and traditions.

Summary. Improving the social pedagogical system of teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan is based on the integration of international requirements and local needs. The theoretical and practical approaches highlighted in this article will help students master foreign languages, as well as prepare them for future professional and social activities. High results can be achieved by introducing innovative methods and modern technologies into the educational process. In teaching foreign languages at school, it is necessary to improve the social pedagogical system, to improve students' language skills, to contribute to their social development, and to prepare them for successful communication in the global environment. Development of this system in grades 10-11 helps to enrich the process of foreign language teaching not only from linguistic, but also from cultural and social aspects. Teachers should organize an effective educational process through the use of innovative methods, individual approach to students and group work. Through this, students learn not only theoretical, but also practical and social aspects of learning a foreign language. Improving the social pedagogical system in teaching foreign languages creates opportunities for students of 10-11 grades not only to learn a language, but also to develop their social skills and successfully express themselves in the global environment. It is possible to improve the effectiveness of foreign language teaching by using new pedagogical methods, technologies and strengthening the social pedagogical system.

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